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WOUND CARE: THE SPECIFICITY OF ONCOLOGICAL LESIONS

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Introduction: Oncological wounds result from the infiltration of malignant cells into the epithelial tissue, compromising its integrity. They affect between 5% and 10% of cancer patients, appearing both in the early stages, such as skin cancer, and in the final phase of the disease, through metastases. Due to the poor prognosis of these lesions, which generally do not heal, palliative care is needed to relieve symptoms, reduce complications and improve the quality of life of patients and their families. **Objective:** To specify the types of lesions and tumors that are essential for planning actions aimed at caring for people with tumor wounds and to contribute to professional qualification, improved care and the satisfaction of patients and their families, meeting their needs more effectively. **Method and materials:** This is a bibliographical study conducted through a systematic search of academic databases, including PubMed, Scopus and Web of Science. The search terms used included "oncological wounds", "nursing care", "treatment of tumor lesions", among others. Studies were selected that addressed wound care in cancer patients, with a special focus on nursing care and best treatment practices. Analysis of the articles included identifying trends, gaps in knowledge and recommendations for clinical practice. **Results:** Oncological wound care demands a specialized and multidisciplinary approach, with emphasis on the crucial role of the nursing team. The evidence highlights the importance of a holistic assessment of patients, considering not only the physical dimension of the wounds, but also the emotional, social and psychological aspects. In addition, gaps in knowledge and clinical practice were identified, highlighting the need for further research and the development of specific guidelines for the treatment of these injuries. **Conclusion:** Given the complexity of cancer wounds and the scarcity of studies on the subject, this review reinforces the urgency of investing in research and continuing education for health professionals. It is essential to promote an integrated approach to the care of these patients, prioritizing symptom relief, pain control and improved quality of life. At the same time, it is crucial to actively involve patients and their families in the care process, ensuring patient-centered care and adequate support throughout the course of the disease.

Keywords: Oncological Tumor Wounds; Nursing Care; Cancer.